

Protected Areas and Prime Hoverfly Areas - safe haven for hoverflies or not?

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Keywords:	area size, comparison, conservation, efficiency, Syrphidae
Abstract:	<p>Efficiency of protected areas has often been questioned due to global decline of biodiversity. Invertebrates, especially insects, have been historically underrepresented in conservation studies. Our study focuses on hoverflies, important group of insect pollinators, which have been proven as good bioindicators as well. Research was focused in Serbia, one of European hotspots of hoverfly diversity, with a long tradition of hoverfly research, which provided sufficient information for conducting our aims: identifying areas of high hoverfly diversity, evaluating the efficiency of Protected and Prime Hoverfly Areas in conservation of hoverflies, determining how well do they cover the distribution of hoverfly species, especially those of conservation concern and testing the importance of the size of the area for conservation of hoverfly diversity. We applied weighting of the species to help stress the importance of species of conservation concern. The results indicated that PHAs cover the areas with high hoverfly diversity better than PAs network, especially when it comes to species of conservation concern. Area size showed slight correlation to hoverfly diversity in case of PHAs, but no correlation was found between size of PAs and hoverfly diversity. This indicates that area size is important when designating new areas important for conservation, but there are also other factors that need to be taken into account, such as habitat quality or suitability. Studies like this are useful in aiding designation of new areas important for conservation of certain species and in identifying sampling gaps, which could potentially aim future research in that direction.</p>

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1 **Protected Areas and Prime Hoverfly Areas - safe haven for hoverflies or not?**

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9 10 **Abstract**

11 Efficiency of protected areas has often been questioned due to global decline of biodiversity.
12 Invertebrates, especially insects, have been historically underrepresented in conservation studies.
13 Our study focuses on hoverflies, important group of insect pollinators, which have been proven
14 as good bioindicators as well. Research was focused in Serbia, one of European hotspots of
15 hoverfly diversity, with a long tradition of hoverfly research, which provided sufficient
16 information for conducting our aims: identifying areas of high hoverfly diversity, evaluating the
17 efficiency of Protected and Prime Hoverfly Areas in conservation of hoverflies, determining how
18 well do they cover the distribution of hoverfly species, especially those of conservation concern
19 and testing the importance of the size of the area for conservation of hoverfly diversity. We
20 applied weighting of the species to help stress the importance of species of conservation concern.
21 The results indicated that PHAs cover the areas with high hoverfly diversity better than PAs
22 network, especially when it comes to species of conservation concern. Area size showed slight
23 correlation to hoverfly diversity in case of PHAs, but no correlation was found between size of

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3 24 PAs and hoverfly diversity. This indicates that area size is important when designating new areas
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5 25 important for conservation, but there are also other factors that need to be taken into account,
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7 26 such as habitat quality or suitability. Studies like this are useful in aiding designation of new
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9 27 areas important for conservation of certain species and in identifying sampling gaps, which could
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11 28 potentially aim future research in that direction.
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18 30 **Keywords.** area size, comparison, conservation, efficiency, Syrphidae

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29 35 INTRODUCTION

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31 36 Due to ever-rising impact of human activities, biodiversity is tackling with an immense amount
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33 37 of pressure. This is a well documented issue on a global level (Butchart *et al.* 2010; Pimm 2014)
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35 38 which raises the question of long-term conservation of biodiversity. One of the most efficient
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37 39 ways of protecting it is to maintain viable populations in natural ecosystems (Balmford *et al.*
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39 40 1996; Redford & Richter 1999; Groves *et al.* 2003; Rosenzweig 2003). This goal is most easily
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41 41 reached through the designation of protected areas (PAs) which is most common, but still one of
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43 42 the most important conservation strategies (Chape *et al.* 2005; Dudley 2008). However, the
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45 43 efficiency of PAs is often questioned (Andam *et al.* 2008; Stoll-Kleemann 2010), because of the
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47 44 obvious ongoing decline of biodiversity worldwide. On the other hand, with an increasing effort
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49 45 to conserve species, a criteria driven approach, often relying on an expert opinion is increasingly
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51 46 used when forming nature reserves (Galindo-Leal *et al.* 2000; Cowling *et al.* 2003). The most
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Hoverflies in Protected and Prime Hoverfly Areas

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3 47 commonly used approach is based on Important Bird Areas (IBA) concept (Anderson 2002),
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5 48 which was later on applied on other taxa. Both approaches (designation of PAs and criteria driven
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7 49 approach) are mostly focusing on more charismatic species like mammals or birds, leaving the
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9 50 arthropods, especially insects, underrepresented.

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12 51 Hoverflies are widely distributed, diverse insect group. They are considered to be the second
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14 52 most important pollinator group after bees (Larson *et al.* 2001). Although often neglected, they
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16 53 play a significant role in biodiversity in general and agrobiodiversity across the biomes (Ssymank
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18 54 *et al.* 2011). A few characteristics such as wide distribution, differences in environmental
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20 55 requirements of larvae and availability of excellent taxonomic keys (especially for European
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22 56 species), make Syrphidae potentially good bioindicators (Sommaggio 1999; Sommaggio &
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24 57 Burgio 2014; Popov *et al.* 2017). Hoverflies have been a research focus in Serbia since the 1950s
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26 58 (Glumac 1955), which has improved our knowledge of their taxonomy, zoogeography,
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28 59 phylogeny and ecology, while also providing important insight into the complex history of the
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30 60 Serbian landscape (Vujić *et al.* 2016).

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33 61 Serbia is located on the Balkan Peninsula in Southeast Europe. Northern part of the country falls
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35 62 within the Pannonian basin, while the southern part is mostly mountainous. There are over 30
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37 63 mountain tops higher than 2,000 meters. Climatic factors are equally complex with continental
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39 64 climate in the northern part, moderate continental climate in the central part of the country,
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41 65 mountain climate on the higher mountains, and Mediterranean climate breaching through the
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43 66 river basins from the south (Radinović 1979). Complex geological history and diverse habitat
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45 67 present in the Balkan Peninsula, thus reflected in Serbia as well, creates favourable conditions for
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47 68 rich biodiversity (Gaston & David 1994). Vast number of endemic and relict species are
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49 69 significant themselves, but also their ecological characteristics, distribution and origin contribute
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51 70 to region's uniqueness (Savić 2008).

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3 71 In recent years, Serbia followed the initiative for designation of important areas for conservation
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5 72 of various organisms such as birds (Important Bird Areas (IBA) (Anderson 2002)), plants
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7 73 (Important Plant Areas (IPA) (Radford & Odé 2009)) and butterflies (Prime Butterfly Areas
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9 74 (PBA) (Jakšić 2008)). Despite the significant role that hoverflies have in ecosystems (Rotheray &
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11 75 Gilbert 2011), and some of them being recognized as threatened on European level (Speight
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13 76 1989, 2000, 2018; Biesmeijer *et al.* 2006), they are completely absent from international lists
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15 77 such as IUCN Red List, or legal instruments such as Annexes of the EU Habitats Directive. Some
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17 78 of the species have been listed on national Red Lists (Jentzsch 1998; Ssymank & Doczkal 1998;
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19 79 Stuke *et al.* 1998; Doczkal *et al.* 1999; Cederberg *et al.* 2010; Ssymank *et al.* 2011), but further
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21 80 efforts have to be made to ensure the survival of this important insect group.
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26 81 In Serbia, 77 species of hoverflies have been protected by the national law Code on declaration
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28 82 and protection of strictly protected and protected wild species of plants, animals and fungi
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30 83 (Official Gazette of RS, no. 5/2010). In order to improve the conservation status of hoverflies,
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32 84 Vujić *et al.* (2016) identified species of conservation concern and proposed priority areas (Prime
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34 85 Hoverfly Areas- PHA) for their preservation in Serbia, based on long-term monitoring data.
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36 86 Methodology was based on expert opinion and it was part of an ongoing national project -
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38 87 Conservation strategy for protected and strictly protected hoverflies (Insecta: Diptera: Syrphidae)
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40 88 species in Serbia - Case study.
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44 89 The aims of this study are: 1) to identify the areas of high hoverfly diversity in Serbia; 2) to
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46 90 evaluate the efficiency of PAs and PHAs in conservation of hoverfly diversity; 3) to determine
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48 91 how well does the PA and PHA network cover the distribution of hoverfly species, especially
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50 92 those of conservation concern, and 4) to test the importance of the size of the area for
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52 93 conservation of hoverfly diversity.
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95 MATERIAL AND METHODS

96 Species distribution data used for the purpose of the analyses were extracted from the database of
97 the Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad. Database
98 was formed based on the samples collected in the last 60 years of field work, which resulted in
99 more than 400 species registered so far (Vujić *et al.* 2018). Data was checked for inconsistencies.
100 Point data without coordinates were assigned ones where possible using Google Earth (Google
101 Inc 2018), while duplicate or doubtful data were removed. Initial number of records before
102 filtering was 27,523. A total of 7,293 records of 412 species were retained after filtering the data
103 and used in the further analysis. Furthermore, a 5×5 km grid was created, covering the territory of
104 the Republic of Serbia (Fig. 1). The records of species occurrences were mapped on the grid in
105 order to visualize data coverage. Duplicate data were removed from each grid cell in order to
106 avoid overrepresentation of some, usually most common species.

107
108 Figure 1
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110 **Coverage of hoverfly diversity and species of conservation concern by PHA and PA**
111 **network**

112 To visualize the areas of high hoverfly diversity, species were simply given the value of one if
113 present on a certain locality and zero if they are absent. In order to identify areas with the highest
114 concentration of species of conservation concern, a weighting scheme similar to the one used by
115 Miličić *et al.* (2017) was used. The factors considered while assigning weights were: is the
116 species on the Prime hoverfly list or not (see Vujić *et al.* 2016) (yes - one; no - zero), is the
117 species endemic to Southeast Europe or not (yes - one; no - zero), is the species occurring in
118 more than one type of habitat (one habitat type - one; more than one habitat type - zero). Final

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3 119 weight of species is formed as the sum of the values of all three factors. Values ranged from zero
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5 120 to three, with three marking the species with highest conservation value.

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7 121 To determine how well does the network of PAs and PHAs cover the distribution of hoverfly
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9 122 species in Serbia (especially the distribution of species of conservation concern), the values of
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11 123 each grid square were calculated by adding up the value of each species present in the square. In
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13 124 order to point out the importance of areas that harbour few, but very important or endangered
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15 125 species, this procedure was carried out separately with and without weight factors. Next,
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17 126 positions of the PAs and PHAs were randomly changed using a Python script for ArcGIS
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19 127 (version 10.1, Esri 2012) and then overlapped with the grid, and procedure of calculating the
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21 128 value of each square was repeated. Values of all squares with records within PAs and PHAs were
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23 129 added up and compared with sums gained with random positioning that was generated 1,000 ×.
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25 130 The actual value was compared to null distribution by single distribution Students' T test.
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33 132 **Area size and hoverfly diversity**

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35 133 In order to test the importance of area size for conservation of species, observed number of
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37 134 hoverfly species was plotted against the size of PAs and PHAs. Size of PAs was calculated based
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39 135 on a map from the World Database of Protected Areas (UNEP-WCMC 2018) and for the
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41 136 calculation of the size of PHAs map from Vujić *et al.* (2016) was used. Only those areas with
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43 137 more than 15 species were included in the analysis, as they were considered sufficiently surveyed
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45 138 (see Verovnik *et al.* 2011). Pearson correlation coefficient between log transformed size of PAs
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47 139 and PHAs and number of species recorded was calculated.
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51 140 All geospatial analyses were carried out using ArcGIS software (version 10.1, Esri 2012).
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53 141 Statistical analyses were performed using R software (version 3.4.4, R Core Team 2018).
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143 **RESULTS**

144 **Coverage of hoverfly diversity by PHA and PA network**

145 Areas of highest hoverfly diversity were concentrated on mountains Fruška gora, Kopaonik,
146 Malinik - Dubašnica and eastern part of Stara planina (Figs. 2, 3). Other centres of relatively high
147 diversity were scattered throughout the country, with notable concentrations in Deliblatska
148 peščara, Vršачke planine and Svrljiške planine. The squares with both highest diversity and
149 conservation value made up 0.7% of the total number of squares, approximately.

151 Figure 2

153 When it comes to squares with the highest diversity (with values ranging from 88 to 164 per
154 square), 49% are located completely within the PHAs (Fig. 2), while considering squares within
155 the PAs, that percent is slightly lower- 37% (Fig. 3). Randomization of the position of PHA and
156 PA network showed that the value of their true position is statistically significantly different from
157 the values of random distribution ($p < 0.001$).

159 Figure 3

161 **Coverage of the species of conservation concern by PHA and PA network**

162 Our results showed that areas of highest diversity of species of conservation concern were located
163 on Fruška gora, Kopaonik, Malinik - Dubašnica (Figs. 4, 5). The squares with highest
164 conservation value (with values ranging from 62 to 89 per square) make up 0.27% of the total
165 number of squares, 78% of these were settled within the boundaries of PHAs (Fig. 4), while 43%
166 of them were within PAs (Fig. 5). Randomization of the position of PHA and PA network

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3 167 showed that the value of their true position is statistically significantly different from the values
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5 168 of random distribution ($p < 0.001$).
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18 174 **Area size and hoverfly diversity**

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21 175 Data on area size and number of species recorded is given in Table S1. We established there was
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23 176 a moderate positive correlation between the size of PHAs and the number of species recorded
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25 177 ($p < 0.005$, $R = 0.55$) (Fig. 6). Regarding PAs, results of the test did not show statistically
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27 178 significant correlation between area size and the number of species ($p > 0.05$, $R = 0.33$) (Fig. 7).
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33 180 Figure 6
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41 184 **DISCUSSION**

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44 185 Prior to this study, Vujić *et al.* (2016) defined species of conservation concern and PHAs in
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46 186 Serbia based on expert opinion and long-term monitoring. Using the data for species of
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48 187 conservation concern, the value of this network was put to a test. Irreplaceability analysis was
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50 188 employed for this purpose. After this study, a series of targeted surveys followed. In this study,
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52 189 we used a different approach to analyze the effectiveness of PAs and PHAs in conservation of
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54 190 hoverfly species in Serbia. The whole hoverfly dataset for Serbia was used (part of it was
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Hoverflies in Protected and Prime Hoverfly Areas

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3 191 compiled during the targeted surveys). The weighting scheme was used in order to point out the
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5 192 importance of rare and endangered species and avoid overrepresentation of most common ones.
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7 193 This also allowed us to visualize the differences between PHA and PA networks more clearly.
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9 194 Additional surveys and a different approach allowed us to establish certain shortcomings of the
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11 195 PHA and PA networks, but also to detect new hoverfly rich areas which could potentially be
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13 196 designated as new PHAs.
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17 197 **Coverage of hoverfly diversity and species of conservation concern by PHA and PA**
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19 198 **network**

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21 199 Our results indicate that in the case of overall hoverfly diversity both PA and PHA network does
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23 200 relatively well correspond with the areas of high hoverfly diversity. That correspondence is
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25 201 slightly higher when it comes to PHAs. Considering hoverfly species of conservation concern,
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27 202 both networks coincide well with regions of high diversity of these species. However, PHA
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29 203 network covers the areas important for those species evidently better than PAs. Hence, weighting
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31 204 of species helped bring out the difference between PAs and PHAs more clearly. These results are
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33 205 in accordance with studies questioning the effectiveness of PAs across EU (Natura 2000 network
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35 206 - N2000). For bats (Lisón *et al.* 2013; Zehetmair *et al.* 2015), vertebrates (Maiorano *et al.* 2007),
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37 207 invertebrates (Hernández-Manrique *et al.* 2012), birds (Albuquerque *et al.* 2013; Pellissier *et al.*
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39 208 2013), lichens (Rubio-Salcedo *et al.* 2013) and plants (Dimitrakopoulos *et al.* 2004). All authors
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41 209 indicated that N2000 is not entirely adequate for conservation of those species.
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46 210 A study on tropical butterflies showed that only approximately half of high priority areas for
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48 211 butterfly diversity are covered by PAs, while the other half is not under protection
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50 212 (Klorvuttimontara *et al.* 2011). Contrastingly, another study suggested that butterflies are very
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52 213 well covered by N2000 sites. Nevertheless, the study identified a few important areas of high
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54 214 diversity that are not under any form of protection (Verovnik *et al.* 2011). Similarly, our results
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3 215 indicate that some of the squares with higher values of species diversity (ranging from 35 species
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5 216 to a maximum of 164 species per square) are not covered by PAs or PHAs. For example, when it
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7 217 comes to species diversity, the area between the Uvac Nature Reserve and Ozren - Jadovnik
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9 218 Landscape of Outstanding Qualities harbours a significant number of species, but nevertheless is
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11 219 not covered by PAs or PHAs. This was also the case with areas surrounding the Kopaonik
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13 220 mountain, parts of mountain Beljanica in eastern Serbia, while some parts of mountain Juhor in
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15 221 central Serbia do not fall within any PA, but are covered by one PHA. These areas offer a decent
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17 222 amount of suitable habitats for hoverfly species, but were probably overlooked when designating
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19 223 PAs and PHAs.

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23 224 When one considers conservation value of the squares, most of those with the highest or higher
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25 225 values fall within the boundaries of PHAs and PAs. Looking at the map, it is evident that the
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27 226 PHAs has better coverage of the most valuable squares, with the exception of parts of southwest
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29 227 Serbia (mountains Golija, Zlatar and Jadovnik), which are slightly better, but still not satisfyingly
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31 228 covered by PAs.

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35 229 There could be several reasons for overall supremacy of PHA network. For instance, many PAs
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37 230 show complete absence of hoverfly data, which does not come as a surprise since they basically
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39 231 represent individual trees, gardens or alleys. These types of homogeneous habitats in some cases
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41 232 can support diverse pollinator assemblages, but in general have fewer individuals and lower
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43 233 diversity than similar rural habitats (Bates *et al.* 2011). Also, designation of PAs has not always
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45 234 been based on criteria solely designed to conserve diversity. Establishment of these areas is
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47 235 sometimes based on anthropocentric reasons, rather than on systematic conservation planning
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49 236 (Pressey *et al.* 1993; Scott *et al.* 2001; Oldfield *et al.* 2004). Furthermore, many of the large PAs
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51 237 are established in order to preserve other species, such as large carnivores or other mammals,
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53 238 therefore it is not straightforward to presume that these areas are suitable for preservation of other
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Hoverflies in Protected and Prime Hoverfly Areas

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3 239 species, especially insects. This was the case with grassland butterflies in Slovenia, since large
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5 240 proportions of some PAs were covered by closed canopy forests (Verovnik *et al.* 2011). On the
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8 241 other hand, there are many examples where criteria driven, expert based networks largely
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10 242 contribute to conservation of certain species. For instance, IPAs have become means of
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12 243 identifying and communicating the importance of a national or regional network of key sites for
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14 244 wild plants and habitats that together can help to conserve global plant diversity. IPAs are not
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17 245 legal site designation, but in many cases they have been integrated into national conservation
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19 246 planning and monitoring schemes (see Plantlife International 2010a, 2010b). For example, in
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21 247 Belarus all IPAs are now protected by law (Darbyshire *et al.* 2017), and in Romania IPAs have
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23 248 led to the recognition and protection of new critical habitats (Sârbu *et al.* 2007), whilst in Croatia
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25 249 many IPAs were included in the expanded protected area network under the N2000 scheme as
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28 250 part of their accession to the European Union in 2013.
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252 Area size and hoverfly diversity

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35 253 Among 38 PHAs, only two are slightly larger than 50,000 ha and 11 of them are smaller than
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37 254 1,000 ha. Around two thirds of them had sufficient number of records (>15). Out of 321 PAs,
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40 255 only three are larger than 50,000 ha and majority of them are smaller than 100 ha. Therefore, it is
41
42 256 no surprise that most of the PAs have no or just sporadic records (<15) of hoverflies. This is in
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44 257 accordance with the results of Krauss *et al.* (2003) and Meyer *et al.* (2005) who found a strong
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47 258 positive relationship between area size and species richness of butterflies, hoverflies and bees.
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49 259 These insects have complex resource and habitat requirements, which change during their life
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51 260 cycle (Steffan-Dewenter *et al.* 2002; Öckinger *et al.* 2012). In other words, they need different
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54 261 resources that are often spatially separated.
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3 262 However, hoverfly diversity in small size PHAs is comparatively large if one considers their size.
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5 263 Some examples are Petrovaradinski rit with 61 species on 684 ha and Avala with 23 species on
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7 264 691 ha. Similarly, the results of a study on butterflies also showed that a few small areas can host
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10 265 high butterfly diversity and could play an important role as source populations in a wider
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12 266 countryside (Verovnik *et al.* 2011). A study on leafhoppers showed that small patches of habitats
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14 267 can have relatively high diversity of generalist species. They found that many leafhopper species
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16 268 are able to cope with the small fragment size as long as a sufficient amount of their host plant is
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18 269 present (Rösch *et al.* 2013). Zulka *et al.* (2014) underlined that there is a dichotomy between size
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20 270 and quality measures present in studies dealing with patch size. Consequently, fragmentation
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22 271 theory is couched in size measures, such as the size of the local habitat patch or the total area of
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24 272 stepping stones, typically without considering variation in habitat conditions (Hanski 1998).
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26 273 The areas holding the highest diversity and at the same time covering the largest surface were
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28 274 Kopaonik, Malinik - Dubašnica, eastern part of Fruška gora and Stara planina. This is somewhat
29
30 275 expected since Kopaonik is considered to be a prime center of biodiversity (Amidžić 2007),
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32 276 Malinik - Dubašnica are considered to be one of the hotspots of biodiversity in the eastern part of
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34 277 Serbia, harbouring a great number of endemic and rare species, Fruška gora has a rich and
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36 278 diverse flora and fauna (Butorac 2007; Habijan-Mikeš 2007) and Stara planina has a status of
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38 279 significant international region (parts of a mountain are part of IBA, IPA and PBA networks)
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40 280 (Stankov *et al.* 2010).
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42 281 Considering PAs, two relatively small areas stood out with relatively high number of species,
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44 282 Avala and Košutnjak. Interestingly, Lazarev kanjon covers a small area, but has harboured the
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46 283 second highest number of species recorded in PAs. Ecological value of this area is highly rated
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48 284 and the reason for this is the rich biodiversity with a high number of endemic and relict species
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285 (Tomić 2011). Few larger areas had high numbers of species recorded: Fruška gora, Kopaonik,
286 and Stara planina. These areas once again confirm their biological value.

287 As mentioned, hoverflies are good bioindicators and one of the best studied groups of insects in
288 Serbia. Serbia has the largest hoverfly database in Southeast Europe, but still cannot be compared
289 with some European countries with much larger and more complete data. The surveys done up
290 until present day in the country were not entirely systematic, as some remote areas were visited
291 only once, or not even once, while some were repeatedly visited due to easier access or well
292 documented hoverfly diversity. Nevertheless, studies like this are useful in identifying areas
293 which are lacking data so that future research can be aimed in that direction. With additional
294 records it is possible that some new hoverfly hotspots will be discovered, which would surely
295 contribute to conservation of this important insect group in Serbia.

296

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478 Table S1 Size of the PAs and PHAs and the number of species recorded within them.

Name	Area in ha	Number of species
PAs		
Košutnjak	265.11	32
Avala	490.86	23
Rusanda	1 159.3	20
Lazarev kanjon	1 809.16	211
Dolina Pčinje	2 633.96	17
Vršačke planine	4 412.08	128
Carska bara	4 723.34	27
Rtanj	5 412.69	22
Koviljsko-Petrovaradinski rit	5 883.02	28
Sićevačka klisura	7 731.88	28
Kamena Gora	7 777.59	56
Kopaonik	11 963.47	242
Vlasina	12 807.24	86
Suva planina	18 158.91	35
Gornje Podunavlje	19 362.61	21
Tara	24 961.13	93
Fruška gora	26 656.42	176
Deliblatska peščara	35 273.93	74
Đerdap	63 705.61	61
Golija	75 881.27	108
Stara planina	113 240	174
PHAs		
Rtanj	366.62	15
Koviljsko-petrovaradinski rit	684.39	61
Avala	691	23
Seličevica	1 412.31	46
Jegrička	1 534.68	43
Juhor	2 886.85	48
Jelašnička klisura	3 250.1	69
Pčinja	7 141.24	23
Vršačke planine	7 411.15	147
Vlasina	8 125.13	63
Debeli lug	8 186.58	78
Svrljiške planine	17 818.72	34
Tara	18 738.05	95
Fruška gora	19 230.82	182
Kopaonik	22 188.33	248
Malinik-Dubašnica	22 496.94	226
Stara planina	26 243.78	172
Deliblatska peščara	33 825.19	68
Šar-planina	52 604.99	114
Đerdap	58 680.37	61

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Hoverflies in Protected and Prime Hoverfly Areas

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3 481 Figure legends
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5 482 Figure 1 Species occurrences in the study area
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7 483 Figure 2 Map of overall diversity of hoverfly species (without weighting factors) in relation to
8 PHA. Squares with records within PHA network are coloured in different shades of gray, those
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12 485 with records outside of PHA network are marked with different patterns.
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14 486 Figure 3 Map of overall diversity of hoverfly species (without weighting factors) in relation to
15 PAs. Squares with records within PA network are coloured in different shades of gray, those with
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19 488 records outside of PAs network are marked with different patterns.
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21 489 Figure 4 Map of diversity of hoverfly species of conservation concern (with weighting factors) in
22 relation to PHAs. Squares with records within PHA network are coloured in different shades of
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26 491 gray, those with records outside of PAs network are marked with different patterns.
27

28 492 Figure 5 Map of diversity of hoverfly species of conservation concern (with weighting factors) in
29 relation to PAs. Squares with records within PAs network are coloured in different shades of
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33 494 gray, those with records outside of PAs network are marked with different patterns.
34

35 495 Figure 6 The relation between number of species recorded and the size of PHAs
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37 496 Figure 7 The relation between number of species recorded and the size of PAs
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